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To cite this article: Nursen Bayazit *et al* 2025 *Meas. Sci. Technol.* **36** 076012

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A novel framework for the uncertainty evaluation of virtual flow meters

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Received 7 March 2025, revised 6 June 2025

Accepted for publication 30 June 2025

Published 14 July 2025

CrossMark

Abstract

The focus on virtual experiments (VEs) utilized for flow measurement in industrial applications is increasingly growing in the context of Industry 4.0 and the European Green Deal. They enable the replacement of cost-intensive physical measurements with computational models. However, the reliability of these virtual flow measurements depends—just as for physical measurements—highly on robust uncertainty quantification. This study introduces a novel framework for uncertainty evaluation that integrates the law of propagation of uncertainty for linear systems and the propagation of distributions for nonlinear systems, following the guide to the expression of uncertainty in measurement. Within this framework, a virtual calibration approach is incorporated that allows the determination of the fluid mechanical calibration factor from VEs instead of cost-intensive measurements. A case study with different Reynolds numbers and geometric configurations demonstrates that the proposed uncertainty evaluation methods perform equally well for an ultrasonic flow meter benchmark application. The proposed approach offers the flexibility to include further error and uncertainty sources, like modeling errors or uncertainties due to missing information in the description of the measurement set-up. Hence, it underscores the potential of VEs in flow measurement towards the virtual calibration of flow meters in complex industrial settings.

Keywords: uncertainty evaluation, flow measurement, virtual experiment, virtual metrology

1. Introduction

Ultrasonic clamp-on flow meters are used for non-invasive flow measurements in various industrial applications, e.g. in the oil and gas industry, chemical industry, water and wastewater industry, food and beverage industry, metal and mining industry, marine industry, life sciences industry, power generation, sustainable energies, heating, ventilation and air conditioning [1]. Flow meters are usually calibrated under

ideal flow conditions that do not necessarily correspond to the real flow conditions in the field [2]. The presence of bends, junctions and other installations can lead to asymmetric velocity distributions and thus to measurement errors [3]. The measurement errors can be corrected with fluid mechanical calibration factors if the local velocity distribution is known [4]. These fluid mechanical calibration factors can be determined experimentally, using complex and costly measurements or by computational fluid dynamics (CFD) simulations. In the latter case, the entire physical system is modeled in a virtual experiment (VE), applying the measurement principle to the calculated flow field. This offers the flexibility to determine the required fluid mechanical calibration factors for various complex configurations [5].

CFD simulations can predict the flow profile for the entire domain, ensuring detailed insights into complex structures such as turbulence, boundary layer or swirl behavior, which

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are challenging to capture in the measurement of practical pipe configurations [6]. Furthermore, CFD simulations offer flexibility in parameter selection and enable the simultaneous investigation of multiple experimental configurations [7]. However, using CFD necessarily implies a degree of simplification for the actual physical system [8]. The approximation of fluid flows by discretized numerical models is limited, e.g. due to grid resolution [9]. The capture of greater detail at a higher computational cost and time is achievable with finer grids but is often not practicable [10]. Direct numerical simulation, i.e. resolving all scales of turbulence, is mainly feasible for simple geometries, though advancements like grid refinement have enabled studies of more complex flows [8]. The selection of a turbulence modeling approach, such as Reynolds-averaged Navier–Stokes (RANS) simulation, large eddy simulation (LES) [11] or hybrid modeling approaches, also impacts the quality of the results, see [8, 12, 13] for further details. While RANS is a computationally efficient approach, it may fail to capture critical turbulent structures, as it does not resolve turbulence directly but relies on turbulence models to determine the mean flow field correctly. In contrast, LES and hybrid models provide higher accuracy but require substantial computational power. Poor quality of boundary conditions and input parameters, such as viscosity or inlet velocity, may not reflect the actual physical domain. Therefore, it is essential to validate CFD studies against experimental data to ensure the reliability of the results [10, 12].

In metrology, confidence in the results of the measurement is established by a quantified statement of its associated uncertainty [14]. The de facto standard for the evaluation of uncertainties in metrology is provided in the guide to the expression of uncertainty in measurement (GUM) [14] and its supplements. Existing studies comprehensively address how uncertainty evaluation can be performed using VEs in conjunction with real measurement data [15, 16] and whether these approaches comply with the methodologies defined in the GUM or its supplements [17]. These studies employ techniques such as Monte Carlo sampling [17–19], Bayesian inference [20] and Fourier analysis [16] to address complex challenges, including nonlinear models [21, 22]. These methods have been applied in different metrological applications, e.g. optical metrology [16, 23, 24], coordinate measuring machines [18, 25–27], computational quantum chemistry [28] or nanoindentation measurements [29, 30].

In the context of flow meters, VEs are often used to quantify uncertainty contributions of the flow rate for conditions that are difficult to investigate experimentally [5, 31, 32]. In [3], a first approach can be found to quantify and reduce uncertainties of the flow rate prediction under disturbed flow conditions for flow measurements. However, to trust a correction of the measured flow rate by the bias predicted in CFD simulations, it is necessary to validate them and, in addition, provide a quantitative statement of the associated uncertainty of the overall result. In [33], a virtual flow meter (i.e. a replacement of a real flow meter measurement process by a simulation) was applied to an ultrasonic clamp-on flow sensor installed

downstream of a double bend out-of-plane. The overall uncertainty of the virtual flow meter was quantified by comparing its output to a traceable reference measurement from a calibrated electromagnetic flow meter (KROHNE WATERFLUX 3070). The approach shows how cost-intensive measurements can be replaced by CFD simulations if an appropriate uncertainty evaluation is performed.

This work develops a generalized framework for the uncertainty evaluation of virtual flow meters. In this approach, VEs are used for the determination of fluid mechanical calibration factors instead of cost-intensive measurements. The method allows the simultaneous application of the law of propagation of uncertainty (LPU) and the propagation of distributions (PoD), where the latter abbreviation is used according to [34]. While the LPU is recommended by the GUM and relies on linearization and the propagation of (co-)variances, the PoD is the recommended approach for uncertainty evaluation in Supplement 1 to the GUM [35] and suitable also for nonlinear models of the measurand, as is the case for flow measurements. Moreover, the PoD, implemented as a Monte Carlo sampling, naturally enables the provision of probability statements, such as coverage intervals.

In contrast to previous investigations, this work systematically performs uncertainty evaluation with different underlying assumptions and provides an approach to directly integrate the VE into the calibration strategy. The key innovation of this contribution is the development of a unified framework that enables uncertainty evaluation across various configurations and flow scenarios rather than being limited to specific cases. For this purpose, the proposed framework is demonstrated using a representative example. While the approach is showcased in a specific case, it can be easily adapted to other applications by modifying the VE component accordingly. In particular, the study highlights differences between scenarios with and without a given fluid mechanical calibration factor, as well as the distinction between linear and nonlinear systems.

The structure of the paper is as follows: section 2 introduces the instrument under examination, namely the ultrasonic flow meter. Section 3 examines the terminology used to describe uncertainty in measurement and applies these definitions to physical and virtual measurements. Section 4 focuses on the uncertainty evaluation methods. Subsequently, sections 5 and 6 present the case study and results, demonstrating and analyzing the applicability of the proposed approaches. In conclusion, section 7 presents the findings and discusses future research directions.

2. Ultrasonic flow meter

This section presents the measurement principle of ultrasonic flow meters and the determination of the fluid mechanical calibration factors. For the latter case, two types are distinguished: the determination of the fluid mechanical calibration factors by means of reference measurements and their determination by means of VEs.

Figure 1. Schematic drawing of the (virtual) flow rate measurement by an ultrasonic flow meter.

2.1. Measurement principle

The fundamental principle for transit time ultrasonic flow meters is measuring the time difference between upward and downward ultrasonic signals. This time difference is directly related to the average velocity along the ultrasonic path, which, in turn, allows for the calculation of the flow rate. The average flow velocity along the measurement path v_{path} is determined using the transit time difference Δt , according to

$$v_{\text{path}} = \frac{l}{2 \cos(\alpha)} \frac{\Delta t}{t_{\text{BA}} t_{\text{AB}}}, \quad (1)$$

where l is the effective length of the ultrasonic path through the fluid, α is the angle between the ultrasonic path and the pipe wall and t_{BA} and t_{AB} are the transit times of the ultrasonic signal against and in the direction of the flow emitted by the upstream transducer A and downstream transducer B, respectively. The transit time difference $\Delta t = t_{\text{BA}} - t_{\text{AB}}$ is proportional to the flow velocity and consequently to the flow rate, with k acting as a proportionality factor that ensures v_{path} corresponds to the volumetric flow rate Q . The flow rate, designated as Q , is then calculated as follows

$$Q = k A v_{\text{path}}, \quad (2)$$

where k is the fluid mechanical calibration factor and A is the cross-sectional area of the pipe. Figure 1 illustrates the measurement setup for a detailed V-type ultrasonic flow meter.

2.2. Fluid mechanical calibration model using reference measurements

Since Δt is influenced by the local velocity distribution along the ultrasonic path, fluid mechanical calibration factors are utilized to take the influence of disturbed flow conditions into account. In an experimental setup, the fluid mechanical calibration factor k can be determined by the ratio of the reference flow rate Q_{ref} of the test rig and the measured flow rate Q_{meas} provided by the ultrasonic flow meter,

$$k = \frac{Q_{\text{ref}}}{Q_{\text{meas}}} = \frac{Q_{\text{ref}}}{A v_{\text{path}}}. \quad (3)$$

Note that the fluid mechanical calibration factor k depends on the piping geometry, measurement position, etc. Hence, it needs to be determined separately for each installation position using the flow rates provided by the ultrasonic flow meter and the reference measurements of the test rig.

2.3. Fluid mechanical calibration model using VEs

As an alternative to cost-intensive measurements, the fluid mechanical calibration factor k can be determined using high-quality CFD simulations or, to reduce computational costs, via VEs that employ surrogate models trained on such simulations. In this paper, a surrogate model from a previous study is used [5], which is shortly summarized in the following. This model is able to predict velocity profiles downstream of various pipe configurations. It is based on 263 CFD simulations of different geometries covering a variety of different single elbow, double s-elbow and double elbow out-of-plane configurations. The principle of the surrogate model involves splitting the velocity profiles into a fully developed and a disturbed part. This offers the advantage of varying the Reynolds number, the roughness of the pipe wall and other parameters independently. For a real-time data assessment and prediction of different flow meter types at arbitrary installation positions, an interpolation of the coefficients from a proper orthogonal decomposition is used to predict the velocity profile in the entire measurement section. Applying the ultrasonic measurement principle to the calculated flow field provides the path velocity and the corresponding fluid mechanical calibration factor. While flow meters are designed to measure the flow rate Q , this quantity is converted into the Reynolds number for the VE, enabling the use of a dimensionless parameter that is not only direct input to the surrogate model, but also provides compatibility between the models introduced in section 3.

The numerical approach to determine the fluid mechanical calibration factor k , when the reference flow rate Q_{ref} is

Figure 2. Flow chart of the DA representing the experimental flow measurement.

unknown, utilizes an iterative optimization. Here, k is determined iteratively by adjusting the Reynolds number Re until the predicted path velocity aligns with the measured path velocity v_{path} , which is obtained using the surrogate model. This enables an accurate Reynolds number estimation under disturbed flow conditions. For a detailed description of this process, the reader is referred to section 3.5.

This approach represents a first step towards the inclusion of VEs into the calibration process of flow meters. It is obvious that the errors and uncertainties related to the VE need to be taken into account before this approach can substitute real calibrations. Furthermore, additional sources of uncertainty arising from an imperfect mapping between the real measurement set-up and its virtual representation need to be taken into account. Nevertheless, the proposed framework shows how cost-intensive measurements to determine the fluid mechanical calibration factor k can be substituted by VEs.

3. Uncertainty evaluation framework

In this work, an uncertainty evaluation framework is developed that allows the application of uncertainty evaluation approaches as recommended in the GUM [14], i.e. the LPU method, and the supplement 1 of the GUM [35], i.e. the Monte Carlo sampling. Hence, the corresponding terminology, quantities and models are introduced for the flow measurement benchmark application.

3.1. Model for the measurand

The model for the measurand describes the functional relationship between the measurand, i.e. the quantity to be measured, and all known input quantities. The latter comprises quantities with type A information, such as the measured path velocity, for which observations are available, and quantities with type B information, for which a value and corresponding uncertainty can be obtained by other means, such as certificates, expert knowledge and empirical data. Examples of these latter quantities are the geometrical properties of the pipe and the kinematic viscosity of the fluid. In this work, the model for the measurand will, according to the notation of [30, 34], also be denoted as the data analysis (DA), motivated by statistical

inference that has to be applied for a flow measurement. While the DA models the functional relationship between the measurand and its affecting input quantities, the VE produces observations of the measured quantity, given specific values for the measurand and the additional input quantities. The following two paragraphs define DA and VE for the flow application. Following and building upon these definitions, the fluid mechanical calibration factor, which can be employed using two different approaches, is defined in the subsequent paragraphs.

3.2. Experimental flow measurement – DA

The DA aims to experimentally determine the measurand Y with the installed ultrasonic flow meter. For the flow meter, the DA is given by

$$Y = f(X, \mathbf{Z}_{0,1}, k), \quad (4)$$

where the measurand Y , which, for the considered flow application, is the Reynolds number, a dimensionless representation of the flow rate Q . It is determined from the measured quantity X , i.e. the path velocity, and the input quantities $\mathbf{Z}_{0,1} = (Z_0, Z_1)$ and k . The function f is given by

$$f(X, \mathbf{Z}_{0,1}, k) = k X \frac{Z_0}{Z_1}, \quad (5)$$

where Z_0 is the inner diameter of the pipe, Z_1 is the kinematic viscosity of the fluid and k is the fluid mechanical calibration factor, see table 1 for more details. The algorithm for the experimental flow measurement, i.e. the DA, is shown in figure 2.

3.3. Virtual flow measurement – VE

The VE is a virtual realization of a measurement process that makes it possible to generate virtual observations of a quantity that would also be observed in a real measurement. The virtually measured values (virtual observations) should have the same metrological properties and quality as the measured values from real measurements, provided that the VE has the same metrological properties and quality assurance methods as the real measuring instrument. This includes properties such

Figure 3. Flow chart of the VE representing the virtual flow measurement.

Figure 4. Flow chart of the CA representing the experimental determination of the fluid mechanical calibration factor.

as stability, drifts and distortions [30]. The VE of the flow meter is symbolized by

$$X_{VE} = g(Y, Z_{2,3,4,5}), \quad (6)$$

where X_{VE} is the virtually measured path velocity, Y the measurand, i.e. the Reynolds number, and $Z_{2,3,4,5}$ the flow input quantities, which include the geometrical parameters and fluid properties of the considered configuration that affect the measurement. A detailed breakdown of the quantities, their values and associated uncertainties can be found in table 1. Further, figure 3 illustrates the algorithm for the virtual flow measurement, i.e. the VE.

Since the path velocity within the surrogate model is determined by the sum of the disturbed and undisturbed velocity components, see section 2.3, the function g can be further decomposed into individual components:

$$g(Y, Z_{2,3,4,5}) = g_d(Y, Z_{2,3,4,5}) + g_u(Y, Z_{2,3,4,5}), \quad (7)$$

$$X_{VE} = X_d + X_u, \quad (8)$$

where $g_d(Y, Z_{2,3,4,5})$ is the function for the disturbed velocity component X_d and $g_u(Y, Z_{2,3,4,5})$ the function for the undisturbed velocity component X_u . Alongside the virtually measured path velocity X_{VE} , the components X_d and X_u can be obtained by the VE model as well. Using this terminology, we can now formally introduce the CAs from sections 2.2 and 2.3.

3.4. Calibration model – CA

The calibration model (CA) determines the fluid mechanical calibration factor k experimentally, see equation (3). In addition to the previously introduced quantities, this approach requires the knowledge of the reference flow rate Q_{ref} , from which the reference Reynolds number Y_{ref} is determined straightforwardly by using the following formula:

$$Y_{ref} = \frac{Q_{ref} Z_0}{A Z_1}, \quad (9)$$

where Z_0 denotes the inner diameter of the pipe, $A = \pi (Z_0/2)^2$ its cross-sectional area and Z_1 the kinematic viscosity of the fluid. Suppose the reference flow rate Q_{ref} as well as the viscosity of the fluid Z_1 and the inner pipe diameter Z_0 are given. In that case, the fluid mechanical calibration factor can be determined analytically as

$$k = h(X, Y_{ref}, Z_{0,1}), \quad (10)$$

where the function h is given by

$$h(X, Y_{ref}, Z_{0,1}) = \frac{Y_{ref} Z_1}{X Z_0}. \quad (11)$$

The implementation of the CA follows the algorithm shown in figure 4.

3.5. Calibration model using a VE – CAVE

The CAVE is needed if the reference flow rate Q_{ref} cannot be determined experimentally. In this case, the fluid mechanical calibration factor is determined by a VE, which is, in the case of a flow meter, usually based on CFD simulations. In this paper, we use the surrogate model from [5], see section 2.3, as the VE model to determine the fluid mechanical calibration factor. In this approach, the fluid mechanical calibration factor k is written as the product of two components: $k = k_u k_d$, where k_u represents the undisturbed, fully developed turbulent flow and k_d represents specific flow disturbances. Following the approach introduced in [5], the undisturbed part of the flow field can be modeled using the semi-analytical approach of Gersten and Herwig [36], which only depends on the Reynolds number and the wall roughness, see also [37]. On the other hand, the disturbed part of the flow field is assumed to be independent of the Reynolds number and can be determined by the specific geometry configuration.

The approach introduced in [5], applied and adapted in this study, determines the fluid mechanical calibration factor k by connecting the VE and the DA model. The VE model provides both the individual components and total fluid mechanical calibration factor through the specific relationship between the velocity and fluid mechanical calibration components:

I. Disturbed fluid mechanical calibration component k_d :

$$k_d = \frac{g_u(Y, \mathbf{Z}_{2,3,4,5})}{g(Y, \mathbf{Z}_{2,3,4,5})} = \frac{X_u}{X_{\text{VE}}}. \quad (12)$$

II. Disturbed flow conditions occur due to the influence of e.g. bends, junctions and other installations on the flow profile, leading to inaccuracies in flow measurement. To determine the disturbed fluid mechanical calibration component k_d , it is essential to assess the impact of these disturbances on the flow profile. This involves comparing the flow with the theoretical fully developed flow profile under disturbed conditions.

III. Undisturbed fluid mechanical calibration component k_u :

$$k_u = \frac{1}{g_u(Y, \mathbf{Z}_{2,3,4,5})} \frac{Y Z_1}{Z_0} = \frac{1}{X_u} \frac{Y Z_1}{Z_0}. \quad (13)$$

IV. Under fully developed flow conditions, the disturbed fluid mechanical calibration component k_d equals 1, indicating no disturbance corrections are needed. The undisturbed fluid mechanical calibration component k_u is determined by comparing the measured fully developed flow with the theoretical fully developed flow under ideal conditions.

V. Fluid mechanical calibration factor k :

$$k = k_d k_u = \frac{1}{g(Y, \mathbf{Z}_{2,3,4,5})} \frac{Y Z_1}{Z_0} \quad (14)$$

$$= \frac{1}{X_{\text{VE}}} \frac{Y Z_1}{Z_0}. \quad (15)$$

VI. The fluid mechanical calibration factor k combines the effects of disturbed and undisturbed conditions. It is

determined by the product of the disturbed and undisturbed fluid mechanical calibration components.

Since the disturbed component k_d is only depending on the disturbance, it is determined once, based on an initially estimated Reynolds number Y_0 and the given input quantities \mathbf{Z} . As a result, only the undisturbed component k_u depends on the actual Reynolds number. This component is iteratively adjusted until the predicted path velocity X_{VE} aligns with the measured path velocity X .

To determine the fluid mechanical calibration factor k for a measured quantity X , i.e. the path velocity, and the corresponding measurand Y , i.e. the Reynolds number, the input quantities \mathbf{Z} and the DA function (5) can be employed. However, since no reference measurement is available and the measurand Y is *a priori* unknown, the following implicit function is considered

$$m(X, Y, \mathbf{Z}) = Y - X k \frac{Z_0}{Z_1}. \quad (16)$$

Here, Z_0 is the inner diameter of the pipe and Z_1 is the kinematic viscosity of the fluid, see table 1. Since the fluid mechanical calibration factor k is hereby determined using the VE, where an *a priori* unknown measurand Y itself is required as an input, this function is truly implicit. Hence, it needs to be solved iteratively as illustrated in the following and figure 5. In particular, a fixed-point iteration is applied to find a value Y^* for the measurand so that the following relation is fulfilled:

$$0 = m(X, Y^*, \mathbf{Z}). \quad (17)$$

Subsequently, the obtained Y^* is used in equation (15) to calculate a corresponding k^* . The following scheme illustrates how to implement the CAVE.

- (i) **Model function definition:** Define the VE model function g to determine the virtually measured quantity X_{VE} , its undisturbed part g_u to determine X_u and the DA model function f to determine Y .
- (ii) **Assign and initialize:** Assign the measured path velocity to X and the flow parameters, including the geometrical parameters and fluid properties of the considered configuration, to the input quantities \mathbf{Z} . Set $i=0$ and initialize the unknown measurand Y with an initial estimate Y_0 . This estimate will be updated during the iterative process to determine the fluid mechanical calibration factor k . Define the desired accuracy ϵ required for the respective application.
- (iii) **Iteration:** Iteratively, starting with $i=0$, apply the VE, the relationships defined for k , and the DA to find consistent values Y_i and k_i that satisfy equation (17) up to an error of ϵ :

I. [VE]:

$$X_{\text{VE}} = g(Y_0, \mathbf{Z}_{2,3,4,5}) \quad (18)$$

$$X_u^i = g_u(Y_i, \mathbf{Z}_{2,3,4,5}) \quad (19)$$

Figure 5. Flow chart of the CAVE representing the virtual determination of the fluid dynamical calibration factor.

II. [Compute]:

$$k_d = \frac{X_u^0}{X_{VE}} \quad (20)$$

$$k_u^i = \frac{1}{X_u^i} Y_i \frac{Z_1}{Z_0} \quad (21)$$

III. [Compute]:

$$k_i = k_d k_u^i \quad (22)$$

IV. [DA]:

$$Y_{i+1} = f(X, Z_{0,1}, k_i) \quad (23)$$

V. If $\|Y_i - Y_{i+1}\| < \epsilon$:

VI. [Compute Output]: $k = k_d k_u^i$

VII. Else:

VIII. increment i by 1 and go back to I.

errors of the surrogate model, errors and uncertainties in the virtual representation of the instrument, simplifications in the implementation of the measurement principle, interpolations between grid points and approximation errors of the integral. For the sake of simplicity, no errors were attributed to the VE in this study. Hence, following this idealization, no uncertainties are present in the model considered in this paper.

3.7. Uncertainty sources of the DA

For the DA, sources of uncertainty are represented by the uncertainties associated with the measured quantity and input quantities. These include the measured path velocity, fluid mechanical calibration factor, installation angle, distance between the measuring device and the flow disturbance and geometric quantities such as inner pipe diameter, curvature radius and wall roughness. Within the framework of this paper, the considered uncertainties are given in table 1.

The schematic sequence of the CAVE and its iterative adjustment is shown in figure 5.

3.6. Uncertainty sources of the VE

Sources of uncertainty in the VE include modeling errors, i.e. the turbulence model within the CFD, numerical errors,

4. Uncertainty evaluation methods

The evaluation of uncertainty is crucial for quantifying the accuracy of measurements. For this purpose, two methods for uncertainty evaluation are presented for each of the two previously introduced flow measurement benchmark scenarios. In the following, the LPU approach and the PoD approach using

Figure 6. Schematic overview of LPU using DA.

Monte Carlo sampling are described in detail, whereby the extension by incorporating the VE for each method is highlighted. These methods will be used in practical examples in section 6.

4.1. LPU

The LPU provides a framework for evaluating the uncertainty in the results of measurements by using linear sensitivity coefficients and (co-)variance propagation for univariate models (as also presented in the GUM [14]), for multivariate or implicit models (as also presented in supplement 2 of the GUM [38]). The sensitivity coefficients, i.e. the partial derivatives of the model for the measurand, i.e. the DA function f , or the implicit function m , can be calculated numerically or analytically. We assume throughout this work that the required partial derivatives exists. This is not restrictive for our considerations, since the DA function f , given in equation (5), is differentiable in the later chosen estimates. The same holds for the implicit function given in equation (16). For details on the smoothness of the VE and the employed surrogate, we refer to [5]. However, the estimated uncertainty is an approximation, since the LPU method is only exactly applicable when the DA function f is linear. Alternative assumptions and scenarios in which the LPU method yields adequate results, such as having no dominant uncertainty source or the measurand being the sum of multiple normally distributed input quantities, are given in the GUM [14]. However, neither of these cases hold for the considered cases of flow measurements in this benchmark application. Further details can be found in section 6.

LPU using the DA

The following paragraph outlines the practical implementation of the LPU using the DA function $Y = f(X, \mathbf{Z}_{0,1}, k)$, where X

represents the measured path velocity with associated uncertainty u_X , $\mathbf{Z}_{0,1}$ represents the flow quantities with their uncertainties $u_{\mathbf{Z}_{0,1}}$ and k represents the fluid mechanical calibration factor with associated uncertainty u_k . Note that, for the flow application, the path velocity X , the Reynolds number Y and the fluid mechanical calibration factor k are univariate. However, the input quantity $\mathbf{Z}_{0,1}$ is multivariate and $u_{\mathbf{Z}_{0,1}}$ denotes the vector of uncertainties for the individual quantities, i.e. no correlations are considered here. According to the LPU, the uncertainty of the measurand Y is given by

$$u_Y = \left(J^f U (J^f)^T \right)^{\frac{1}{2}}, \quad (24)$$

where J^f denotes the Jacobian of the evaluation function f and $U = \text{diag}(u_X^2, u_{\mathbf{Z}_{0,1}}^2, u_k^2)$ is the diagonal covariance matrix of the measured and input quantities. For illustration, figure 6 presents a flowchart for implementing the LPU using the DA. An algorithmic description for this method can be found in appendix A.

An important assumption for this approach is that this method can only be used if the value of the fluid mechanical calibration factor k and its associated uncertainty are given, e.g. if they have been determined beforehand by comparing the measured flow rate with a reference flow rate, see section 2.2. Otherwise, a VE has to be used to determine the fluid mechanical calibration factor iteratively, see section 2.3. In this case, the LPU approach is extended by including a VE.

LPU using a VE-DA combination

This extension of the LPU approach is used if the fluid mechanical calibration factor k and its associated uncertainty are unknown. In particular, it is assumed that the CAVE of section 3.5 is performed. Since the CAVE is given by an implicit function, appropriate uncertainty evaluation procedures are

Figure 7. Schematic overview of LPU using the VE-DA combination.

required. In this work, we apply the approach presented in supplement 2 of the GUM [38], where the implicit function theorem is utilized to obtain a formulation similar to the LPU. In particular, once an estimate for the involved quantities is determined, the uncertainty for the measurand Y is evaluated according to

$$u_Y = \left(J_Y^{-1} J_{X,Z} U (J_{X,Z})^T J_Y^{-T} \right)^{\frac{1}{2}}, \quad (25)$$

where J_Y and $J_{X,Z}$ are the respective partial derivatives of the implicit function $m(X, Y, Z)$, evaluated at the corresponding estimates. As previously stated with a slight modification in the notation of Z , the matrix U describes the covariance matrix of the variables X and Z .

The following scheme illustrates how the LPU using a VE-DA combination can be implemented.

- (i) **Model function definition:** Define the VE model function g , the DA model function f and the relationship for k expressed in terms of its components k_d and k_u . Define m according to equation (16).
- (ii) **Assign and initialize:** Assign the measured path velocity to X and the flow parameters, including the geometrical parameters and fluid properties of the considered configuration, to the input quantities Z . Initialize the unknown measurand Y with an initial estimate Y_0 . Further, assign the uncertainties according to the quantities X and Z . These quantities and estimates are given from measurements or expert knowledge.

- (iii) **Calculate calibration:** Apply CAVE, see section 3.5, to find consistent values for k and Y that satisfy equation (17) up to the desired accuracy defined in the CAVE model, which yields the estimate \hat{k} .
- (iv) **Calculate DA:** To obtain an estimate for the measurand, compute the DA function $\hat{Y} = f(\hat{X}, \hat{Z}_{0,1}, \hat{k})$, where \hat{X} and \hat{Z} denote the chosen estimates for X and Z .
- (v) **Jacobian calculation:** Compute the Jacobian $J_{X,Z}$ of the model function m with respect to X and Z and its Jacobian J_Y with respect to Y as

$$J_{X,Z} = \left(\frac{\partial m}{\partial X} \Big|_{X=\hat{X}}, \frac{\partial m}{\partial Z} \Big|_{Z=\hat{Z}} \right), \quad (26)$$

$$J_Y = \frac{\partial m}{\partial Y} \Big|_{Y=\hat{Y}}. \quad (27)$$

- (vi) **Covariance matrix calculation:** Construct the covariance matrix U from the uncertainties u_X and u_Z associated with X and Z . Moreover, X and Z are assumed to be independent, which leads to the covariance matrix

$$U = \text{diag}(u_X^2, u_Z^2), \quad (28)$$

- where u_X^2 and u_Z^2 are the variances in X and Z .
- (vii) **Resulting uncertainty:** Propagate the uncertainties in the input variables X and Z through the function m to obtain the resulting uncertainty u_Y in the output variable Y as given in equation (25).

Figure 7 illustrates a schematic overview of how the LPU using the VE-DA combination can be implemented.

4.2. PoD-based methods

PoD-based methods are widely used for uncertainty evaluation and are also described in detail in supplement 1 of the GUM [35]. Numerically, they are implemented using the Monte Carlo method. The principle of these methods is that a probability distribution can be assigned to the input quantities of the model for the measurand, representing its state of knowledge, and subsequently these distributions are propagated through the model. The PoD approach can be applied also to nonlinear DA function f and can hence be considered as an extension of the uncertainty evaluation framework of the GUM to nonlinear measurement models. This is an important property since both, the DA function f and the considered surrogate model from [5] are nonlinear mappings.

PoD applied to DA

In this approach, the uncertainty of the measurand Y is characterized by a state-of-knowledge probability distribution P_Y , which incorporates the uncertainties of the involved measured quantity X and the input quantities $\mathbf{Z}_{0,1}$ and k through the function $f(X, \mathbf{Z}_{0,1}, k)$. The uncertainties in X , $\mathbf{Z}_{0,1}$ and k are modeled by their respective state-of-knowledge probability distributions P_X , $P_{\mathbf{Z}_{0,1}}$ and P_k , respectively. In this work, all of these distributions are assumed to follow a normal distribution.

Assuming a normal distribution for the involved input quantities requires specification of their mean and standard deviation. Since k is either already known (e.g. in terms of a look-up table or expert knowledge) or determined beforehand by the CA model function h , its mean k is treated as a given input quantity alongside its associated uncertainty u_k within the method. Similarly, for the input quantities $\mathbf{Z}_{0,1}$, a mean (using the same symbol) and a covariance matrix $u_{\mathbf{Z}_{0,1}}^2$ are assigned from expert knowledge. For the measured quantity X , the measurement is taken as the mean of P_X and u_X^2 denotes the assigned variance, which is taken from repeated measurements and assumed to be known.

The distribution P_Y is generated by repeatedly sampling values $x_n \sim P_X$, $z_n \sim P_{\mathbf{Z}_{0,1}}$ and $k_n \sim P_k$ and then evaluating them with the function $f(X, \mathbf{Z}_{0,1}, k)$ as

$$y_n = f(x_n, z_n, k_n). \quad (29)$$

The resulting y_n values form a sample of the distribution P_Y . This approach effectively describes the propagation of uncertainty by propagating the distributions P_X , $P_{\mathbf{Z}_{0,1}}$ and P_k through the function $f(X, \mathbf{Z}_{0,1}, k)$ to determine the distribution P_Y of the output quantity Y . With the distribution P_Y , the value for the measurand Y is taken as the mean value and the uncertainty u_Y as the standard deviation.

The algorithm can be implemented as follows:

- (i) **Model function definition:** Define the DA model function f .
- (ii) **Assign:** Assign the measured path velocity to X , the flow parameters, including the geometrical parameters and

fluid properties of the considered configuration, to $\mathbf{Z}_{0,1}$ and the fluid mechanical calibration factor to k . Further, assign the uncertainties according to the quantities X , $\mathbf{Z}_{0,1}$ and k . These estimates are typically derived from measurements or prior knowledge.

- (iii) **Draw samples:** Choose a suitable sample size N . For $n = 1, \dots, N$, draw samples from the distributions of X , $\mathbf{Z}_{0,1}$ and k :

$$x_n \sim \mathcal{N}(X, u_X^2), \quad (30)$$

$$z_n \sim \mathcal{N}(\mathbf{Z}_{0,1}, u_{\mathbf{Z}_{0,1}}^2), \quad (31)$$

$$k_n \sim \mathcal{N}(k, u_k^2). \quad (32)$$

- (iv) **Calculate:** For each sampled pair (x_n, z_n, k_n) calculate the output y_n :

$$y_n = f(x_n, z_n, k_n). \quad (33)$$

- (v) **Resulting uncertainty:** Calculate the mean and standard deviation of the sample (y_1, \dots, y_N) to obtain an estimate \hat{Y} for the measurand Y and its uncertainty u_Y :

$$\hat{Y} = \frac{1}{N} \sum_{n=1}^N y_n, \quad (34)$$

$$u_Y = \left(\frac{1}{N-1} \sum_{n=1}^N (y_n - \hat{Y})^2 \right)^{\frac{1}{2}}. \quad (35)$$

The schematic overview for implementing the PoD applied to DA is illustrated in figure 8. For further details, the reader is referred to the supplement 1 of the GUM [35].

PoD applied to VE, followed by DA

In this approach, in contrast to the PoD applied to the DA approach above, the uncertainty in k is not *a priori* represented by a probability distribution. Instead, k is calculated from x_n and z_n at each sampling step with the CAVE model, see section 3.5. Since k is calculated iteratively from the measured quantity X , input quantities \mathbf{Z} and an initial estimate of the measurand Y_0 for each sample drawing within the CAVE, the probability distribution of k is actually an intermediate result that is subsequently propagated through the model for the measurand f . The distribution P_Y is generated by first sampling $x_n \sim P_X$ and $z_n \sim P_{\mathbf{Z}_{0,1}}$ and then calculating the corresponding value of k_n using CAVE. The final output y_n is obtained by evaluating the function $f(x_n, z_n, k_n)$ as stated in equation (29).

The resulting values y_n form a sample of the distribution P_Y . This method effectively describes the propagation of uncertainty by considering the independent distributions P_X and $P_{\mathbf{Z}_{0,1}}$, along with the deterministic calculation of k processed through the function $f(X, \mathbf{Z}_{0,1}, k)$. With the distribution P_Y , the measurand Y is defined by its mean and the associated uncertainty u_Y is represented by the standard deviation. Even though a VE and numerical optimization, i.e. a fixed-point iteration, are applied within the estimation of the

Figure 8. Schematic overview of PoD applied to DA.

measurand, this procedure can be seen as in line with the uncertainty evaluation framework of supplement 1 of the GUM.

It is to be noted that if one is interested in the properties of the fluid mechanical calibration factor k , one may utilize this approach without the final evaluation of the model for the measurand Y .

For the implementation of this scheme, the following algorithm is suggested:

- (i) **Model function definition:** Define the VE model function g , the DA model function f and the relationship for k expressed in terms of its components k_d and k_u .
- (ii) **Assign and initialize:** Assign the measured path velocity to X and the flow parameters, including the geometrical parameters and fluid properties of the considered configuration, to the input quantities \mathbf{Z} . Initialize the unknown measurand Y with an initial estimate Y_0 . Further, assign the uncertainties according to the quantities X and \mathbf{Z} . These quantities and estimates are given from measurements or expert knowledge.
- (iii) **Draw samples:** Choose a suitable sample size N . For $n = 1, \dots, N$, draw samples from the distribution of X and \mathbf{Z} :

$$x_n \sim \mathcal{N}(X, u_X^2), \quad (36)$$

$$z_n \sim \mathcal{N}(\mathbf{Z}, u_{\mathbf{Z}}^2). \quad (37)$$

- (iv) **Compute k_n :** With the initial estimate Y_0 and for each sample x_n, z_n , compute k_n with the CAVE, see section 3.5.
- (v) **Calculate:** For each sample x_n, z_n and k_n , calculate the output y_n :

$$y_n = f(x_n, z_n, k_n). \quad (38)$$

- (vi) **Resulting uncertainty:** Calculate the mean and standard deviation of y_n to get an estimate \hat{Y} for the measurand Y and its uncertainty u_Y :

$$\hat{Y} = \frac{1}{N} \sum_{n=1}^N y_n, \quad (39)$$

$$u_Y = \left(\frac{1}{N-1} \sum_{n=1}^N (y_n - \hat{Y})^2 \right)^{\frac{1}{2}}. \quad (40)$$

The approach described above captures the interaction of the measured quantity X and input quantities \mathbf{Z} with the virtually determined fluid mechanical calibration factor k , which is adjusted dynamically until it fits the measured path velocity X and given flow parameters \mathbf{Z} . Figure 9 visualizes the scheme for PoD applied to VE, followed by DA.

Figure 9. Schematic overview of PoD applied to VE, followed by DA.

Figure 10. Configuration left to right: single elbow (SE), double s-elbow (DSE), double elbow out-of-plane (DE).

5. Investigation setup

This section introduces the measured and input quantities selected for analyzing the methods for determining the measurand Y and the uncertainty in the measurand u_Y . Further, the case study is selected in such a way that the accuracy and reliability of the methods can be analyzed under various conditions to reproduce real conditions. For this purpose, three operating points were selected at Reynolds numbers of 5×10^4 , 2.5×10^5 and 7×10^5 at the configurations single

elbow, double s-elbow and double elbow out-of-plane, as illustrated in figure 10. The baseline case represents a double elbow out-of-plane setup at $Re = 5 \times 10^4$.

The quantities were selected based on experimental data and prior expert knowledge, which were determined according to user conditions and preliminary investigations [5, 33]. In detail, the quantities are defined based on the experimental measurement setup on the long-term ultrasonic and laser measurement facility test rig at the National Metrology Institute of Germany (PTB). At PTB, the curvature radius

Table 1. Input table for baseline case.

Quantity	Value	Unit	Remark
X	—	(ms^{-1})	Path velocity v_{path} provided from experiment or VE
Y	—	(—)	Reynolds number Re provided as estimate or from DA
Z_0	0.1	(m)	Inner pipe diameter D of test rig
Z_1	0.8×10^{-6}	($\text{m}^2 \text{s}^{-1}$)	Kinematic viscosity ν of water at $T = 30^\circ$
Z_2	1.425	(—)	Normalized curvature radius R_c/D of test rig
Z_3	35.49	(—)	Normalized downstream distance z/D at test rig
Z_4	0	(—)	Normalized distance between two bends d_i/D at test rig
Z_5	18	($^\circ$)	Angular orientation φ of the meter with respect to the upstream bend
k	—	(—)	Fluid mechanical calibration factor
u_x	—	(ms^{-1})	Uncertainty in X
u_{z0}	0.0005	(m)	Uncertainty in Z_0
u_{z1}	0	($\text{m}^2 \text{s}^{-1}$)	Uncertainty in Z_1
u_{z2}	0	(—)	Uncertainty in Z_2
u_{z3}	0.05	(—)	Uncertainty in Z_3
u_{z4}	0	(—)	Uncertainty in Z_4
u_{z5}	3	($^\circ$)	Uncertainty in Z_5
u_k	0	(—)	Uncertainty in k

R_c and the distance between two bends d_i have been measured with very high accuracy. Hence, their uncertainties are sufficiently small to be considered negligible. In the experiments, the flow rate, designated as Q , is measured with an ultrasonic flow meter for several downstream positions and installation angles. For a detailed description of the flow conditions, the flow meter and the measurement setup, please refer to [33]. The selected input values are summarized in table 1. In the proposed framework, the uncertainty for k is assumed to be zero under the premise that it can be measured with sufficient precision in the flow meter benchmark application. This assumption also reflects the conditions that are assumed for the VE, namely that it is exact, i.e. without any errors. Hence, this simplification allows a direct comparison between the simulated experimental and VE-based virtual determination of the fluid mechanical calibration factors since the same measured and input quantities with their associated uncertainties impact the evaluation methods.

6. Results

This section evaluates the performance of the different uncertainty evaluation methods introduced in section 4, enabling a comprehensive understanding of the influences of the various measured and input quantities on the measurand Y and its uncertainty u_Y . The results are verified by comparison with a reference value for each case. Further, the analysis involves a more detailed investigation of a baseline case to underscore the importance of selecting a suitable method regarding specific

practical scenarios and conditions. The investigation includes calculating absolute and relative errors between the calculated measurand Y_{cal} from the methods and the reference measurand value Y_{ref} , comparing the uncertainties u_Y from the methods to each other and evaluating the computation time and practical consideration for each method. Additionally, a full factorial design study to systematically address the influence of the input quantities on the measurand uncertainty u_Y is introduced. Finally, the distribution of the two PoD methods is investigated and statistically analyzed in terms of sample size and simulation runs. The results provide the basis for the subsequent conclusion in section 7.

6.1. Case study

The case study is intended to analyze the methods in specific application contexts, including operation points at Reynolds numbers of 5×10^4 , 2.5×10^5 and 7×10^5 for the configurations single elbow, double s-elbow and double elbow out-of-plane, see section 5. The aim is to verify and compare the methods. The uncertainties of the methods are taken into account in the form of confidence intervals with upper bounds CI_{upper} and lower bounds CI_{lower} , given as $Y_{\text{cal}} \pm k_{\text{CI}} u_Y$ with $k_{\text{CI}} = 1.96$ corresponding to 95% coverage under the assumption of a normal distribution. It was found that the reference value for the measurand Y_{ref} lies within these uncertainty intervals in all cases, see table B1. This indicates that none of the methods show systematic deviations regarding the uncertainty evaluation. The results are visualized in figure 11 using an error bar plot to illustrate the calculated measurand Y_{cal} together with its uncertainty u_Y as calculated by the

Figure 11. Case study results of the flow meter benchmark application.

Table 2. Double elbow out-of-plane (DE) results for operation point $Re = 5 \times 10^4$ (-).

Method	Y_{ref} (-)	Y_{cal} (-)	u_Y (-)	CI_{lower} (-)	CI_{upper} (-)	Time (s)	Sample size
LPU applied to DA	50 078.806	50 078.806	250.823	49 587.193	50 570.418	0.251	1
LPU applied to VE-DA	50 078.806	50 078.795	258.489	49 572.157	50 585.434	31.517	1
PoD applied to DA	50 078.806	50 079.177	251.518	49 586.202	50 572.152	0.402	10^5
PoD applied to VE-DA	50 078.806	50 079.062	258.072	49 573.240	50 584.884	13 306.247	10^5

different methods. Further, a dashed line shows the reference value Y_{ref} for each operation point. The figure shows that the results of the methods across all cases differ only slightly.

In detail, a slight trend within the deviation is apparent. The VE-DA methods, which include the virtual determination of the fluid mechanical calibration factors, tend to have slightly higher uncertainties than the DA methods. This can be attributed to the dependence of the virtual frameworks on model assumptions and approximations, which can introduce additional uncertainties. This difference is noticeable in all nine cases, where the uncertainties obtained by the DA methods consistently show lower overall uncertainties. These findings underscore the inherent influence within the VE-DA methods by numerical errors.

Nevertheless, the overall consistency between the results of table B1 and the graphical representation in figure 11 confirms the methods' reliability. The almost identical results of the measurand Y_{cal} compared to the reference measurand value Y_{ref} and minor deviations of the uncertainties u_Y show that all methods suit the analyzed scenarios.

When choosing a suitable uncertainty evaluating method, it is crucial to identify the most suitable approach depending on the specific scenario and given conditions. The choice of method depends heavily on whether k is a known input quantity or needs to be determined virtually. For this, the methods are further investigated within the baseline case regarding their performance under these two distinct scenarios: (1) when k is experimentally given and uncertainty evaluation with DA methods is applicable or (2) when k is not known, which implies the requirement of uncertainty evaluation with VE-DA methods. Table 2 provides an overview of the baseline

case, including the performance for each method in terms of accuracy, computation time and sample size as key validation metrics. All methods were executed in parallel using 8 logical processors via a multiprocessing pool to provide a comparison of their computational performance. The LPU applied to DA, LPU applied to VE-DA and PoD applied to DA methods were computed on a local PC with an Intel Core i5-10 310U processor, featuring 4 physical cores and 8 logical processors. The PoD applied to VE-DA method was parallelized on a workstation with two AMD EPYC 7702 processors, totaling 128 physical cores and 256 logical processors, with computations explicitly limited to 8 logical processors.

For each method, the absolute error

$$E_{abs} = |Y_{cal} - Y_{ref}| \tag{41}$$

and the relative error (in percent)

$$E_{rel} = \frac{E_{abs}}{Y_{ref}} \times 100\% \tag{42}$$

are calculated.

In scenarios where the LPU and PoD are applied to the DA method, i.e. where the fluid mechanical calibration factor k is determined experimentally, the results show that the LPU achieved perfect accuracy with $E_{abs} = 0$ and $E_{rel} = 0\%$. This was to be expected since LPU requires the fluid mechanical calibration factor to be precisely determined beforehand, ensuring a perfect analytical computation of the output measurand Y . In detail, it means that the input measurand value Y_{ref} of the CA is the output measurand value Y of the LPU method by construction. The PoD applied to DA method produced slightly higher errors of $E_{abs} = 0.371$ and

$E_{\text{rel}} = 7.408 \times 10^{-4}\%$ due to the stochastic nature of Monte Carlo simulations used in PoD. In particular, a sample size of 10^5 leads to differences in the fifth significant digit that may be viewed as random fluctuations. To verify this, an additional analysis using an increased sample size of 10^7 was performed, which yielded more precise results for the measured Y , see section 6.2. This confirms that the initial discrepancies are due to sampling limitations rather than systematic errors. In terms of computation time, the LPU applied to DA method was very fast, requiring only 0.251 s. In this approach, only analytical equations derived from partial derivatives need to be calculated to propagate uncertainties through the model. The LPU applied to DA method avoids the iterative algorithm inherent in the CAVE and stochastic approximations inherent in Monte Carlo simulations, making it computationally highly efficient. The PoD applied to DA method required slightly more time of 0.402 s due to the computational cost of Monte Carlo simulations but remained competitive with the LPU applied to DA method.

In scenarios where the fluid mechanical calibration factor k is not known and needs to be determined virtually (e.g. using the CAVE algorithm), the results highlight that the LPU applied to VE-DA method demonstrated a very high accuracy with $E_{\text{abs}} = 0.011$ and $E_{\text{rel}} = 2.197 \times 10^{-5}\%$. The results were close to the LPU applied to DA approach but showed minor deviations due to the inclusion of the VE. The PoD applied to VE-DA method produced a higher absolute error, with $E_{\text{abs}} = 0.256$ and $E_{\text{rel}} = 5.112 \times 10^{-4}\%$. The combination of Monte Carlo sampling and the iterative algorithm of the CAVE introduced a certain level of computational and sampling errors. In terms of computation time, the LPU applied to VE-DA method is computationally efficient and, hence, practically applicable, taking 31.517 s. In contrast, the PoD applied to VE-DA method was very slow with a computation time of approximately 3.7 h. The combination of Monte Carlo sampling and iterative VE-DA algorithms significantly increases computational demands. However, it is a versatile tool for nonlinear systems and cases with non-Gaussian distributions, making it applicable across a wide range of application scenarios.

The observed trends align with theoretical expectations. VE-DA methods inherently involve iterative algorithms, which require more computation time. Still, VE-DA methods are needed if the fluid mechanical calibration factor is not given. While Monte Carlo simulations are computationally intensive due to the need for large sample sizes to approximate the uncertainty with high precision, they remain advantageous for complex, nonlinear systems where traditional LPU methods are usually not applicable. In contrast, LPU leverages deterministic equations, making it faster and more accurate for problems with well-defined linear relationships. However, approximations of the sensitivity coefficients have to be taken into account, e.g. when computing a numerical gradient of the VE. Overall, practical scenarios and conditions influence the method selection significantly.

Table 3. Sample size validation of case study.

Y			
Method	Sample size	Sample runs	SD
PoD applied to DA	10^5	10	$\leq 0.005\%$
PoD applied to VE-DA	10^5	10	$\leq 0.005\%$
u_Y			
Method	Sample size	Sample runs	SD
PoD applied to DA	10^5	10	$\leq 0.6\%$
PoD applied to VE-DA	10^5	10	$\leq 0.6\%$

In addition to the case study, a two-level full factorial design study was performed to address the specific impacts of the input quantities. Since Z_0 , Z_3 and Z_5 are the only quantities with given uncertainties, $2^3 = 8$ possible combinations were computed. The results of each run are summarized in table C1. The study shows that the input quantity Z_0 has the most dominant impact on the resulting uncertainty of the LPU applied to the VE-DA method. Performing the same design study with a significantly smaller uncertainty $u_{Z_0} = 2 \times 10^{-5}$, see table C2, confirms this observation, since all inputs show a similar influence to the uncertainty u_Y . Comparable results are to be observed for the other uncertainty evaluation methods.

6.2. PoD validation

The distribution of the PoD methods, see figure 12, was visualized using a frequency polygon. The curves follow an almost normal distribution, with confidence intervals matching almost perfectly. The distributions were close together, indicating statistically insignificant differences between the Monte Carlo simulations.

The statistical validation, listed in table 3, was carried out using a sample size of 10^5 and 10 simulation runs. The objective of this sample size is to obtain a robust estimate of the distribution and to enable high precision in the simulation of the measurand Y and prediction of its uncertainty u_Y . The standard deviation (abbreviated as SD in table 3) associated with the measurand Y is less than or equal to 0.005%, the one associated with the measurand uncertainty u_Y is less than or equal to 0.6%.

While both methods provide a reasonable distribution estimate, the PoD applied to DA method shows slight deviations in the estimate of the measurand Y in the fifth significant digit when using 10^5 samples. However, increasing the sample size to 10^7 significantly improves the PoD applied to DA results, with an estimate of the measurand of $Y = 50078.755$ and a corresponding uncertainty of $u_Y = 252.021$. This improvement highlights the inherent advantage of the Monte Carlo-based PoD approach, which aligns well with the recommendations of the GUM. Consequently, the initially observed deviations can be confidently attributed to sampling limitations and do not compromise the overall reliability of the approach.

Figure 12. Probability distribution of the PoD uncertainty evaluation methods.

7. Conclusion

The results of the investigations provided important insights into the reliability and applicability of different uncertainty evaluation methods regarding a flow measurement benchmark application. In particular, the existing GUM approaches were implemented and adjusted to include VEs, resulting in a generalized framework for the uncertainty evaluation of virtual flow meters. In this approach, the fluid mechanical calibration factor does not need to be determined by cost-intensive high-precision measurements beforehand. Instead, its determination is directly included in the process of uncertainty evaluation using VEs. Hence, it is a first step towards the virtual calibration of flow meters.

The evaluation of the case study demonstrated that all the applied methods provide overall consistent results for both the measurand Y value, which nearly agrees with its reference value, and the associated uncertainty u_Y . The study confirms that the reference value always falls within the uncertainty ranges of all methods. The variations in these results are generally minimal, even though the fluid mechanical calibration factor k is incorporated differently in the DA and VE-DA approaches and the mathematical model frameworks of the uncertainty evaluation methods, i.e. the LPU and the PoD, follow different concepts. This consistency highlights the accuracy and reliability of these methods within the flow meter benchmark application across different scenarios. Moreover, this study underscored the importance of selecting the appropriate uncertainty evaluation method based on the specific scenario and given conditions of the application.

This paper provides systematic step-by-step guidance for users, enabling the selection of the appropriate methodology based on the specific scenario, which depends on whether the fluid mechanical calibration factor k is given or not and

whether the system is linear or nonlinear. For experimentally known k , DA methods should be used, with a preference for LPU if the system is linear. If the system is nonlinear, PoD is more appropriate. This aligns with other findings in the literature and confirms that the general approach recommended in the GUM for experimental measurements is also applicable to VEs. For unknown k , VE-DA methods are required, which enable virtual and iterative determination of k via CAVE. While LPU is faster and more efficient for linear systems, PoD is better suited for handling nonlinear systems. In all cases, it is important to identify whether the system behavior is linear or nonlinear. However, it is recommended to perform a comparative calculation using LPU even for nonlinear systems. If the results of LPU and PoD match for a specific setup, LPU can serve as a cost-efficient alternative to Monte Carlo computations for other configurations. This simplifies the process due to its computational efficiency, which is the case of this flow meter benchmark application.

It remains important to note that the verification was conducted only under benchmark conditions, without practical implementation using industrial field measurement data. Consequently, potentially significant factors or interactions present in real-world scenarios may not have been adequately considered. This limitation presents opportunities for future development, especially in adapting the benchmark scenario to practical applications and thus to include influences that stem from considering different types of fluids or other environmental conditions to demonstrate the broad applicability of the proposed methods. Additional sources of uncertainty—such as errors in the determination of the fluid mechanical calibration factors, variations in temperature and pressure, long-term stability of measurement equipment, measurement repeatability and signal processing interference—should be systematically quantified and incorporated into the model.

Data availability statement

The data that support the findings of this study are available from the authors upon reasonable request. At a later stage, the data will be published in an open access repository as part of the European Partnership on Metrology project ‘Trustworthy virtual experiments and digital twins’ (22DIT01 ViDiT).

Acknowledgment

This work was carried out within the project 22DIT01 ViDiT, which has received funding from the European Partnership on Metrology, co-financed from the European Union’s Horizon Europe Research and Innovation Programme and by the Participating State.

Appendix A. LPU applied to DA implementation

The following scheme gives step-by-step guidance on how to implement the LPU using the DA:

- (i) **Model function definition:** Define the model function f that relates the output measurand Y to the measured quantity X and input quantities $\mathbf{Z}_{0,1}$ and k
- (ii) **Assign:** Assign the measured path velocity to X , the flow parameters, including the geometrical parameters and fluid properties of the considered configuration, to $\mathbf{Z}_{0,1}$ and the fluid mechanical calibration factor to k . Further, assign the uncertainties according to the quantities X , $\mathbf{Z}_{0,1}$ and k . These estimates are typically derived from measurements or prior knowledge.
- (iii) **Jacobian calculation:** Compute the Jacobian matrix J^f which consists of the partial derivatives of the model function f with respect to X , $\mathbf{Z}_{0,1}$ and k . Hereby, the Jacobian matrix captures the sensitivity of the output Y to small changes in the inputs X , $\mathbf{Z}_{0,1}$ and k and represents how the function f changes with respect to changes in X , $\mathbf{Z}_{0,1}$ and k . For the flow application, $J^f \in \mathbb{R}^{n+m}$ is given as

$$J^f = \left(\frac{\partial f}{\partial X} \Big|_{X=\hat{X}}, \frac{\partial f}{\partial \mathbf{Z}} \Big|_{\mathbf{Z}_{0,1}=\hat{\mathbf{Z}}_{0,1}}, \frac{\partial f}{\partial k} \Big|_{k=\hat{k}} \right), \quad (\text{A.1})$$

where \hat{X} , $\hat{\mathbf{Z}}_{0,1}$ and \hat{k} denote the chosen estimates for X , $\mathbf{Z}_{0,1}$ and k .

- (iv) **Covariance matrix calculation:** Construct the covariance matrix U from the uncertainties u_X , $u_{\mathbf{Z}_{0,1}}$ and u_k associated with X , $\mathbf{Z}_{0,1}$ and k . Since X , $\mathbf{Z}_{0,1}$ and k are independent, U is a diagonal matrix:

$$U = \text{diag} \left(u_X^2, u_{\mathbf{Z}_{0,1}}^2, u_k^2 \right), \quad (\text{A.2})$$

where u_X^2 , $u_{\mathbf{Z}_{0,1}}^2$ and u_k^2 are the variances in X , $\mathbf{Z}_{0,1}$ and k .

- (v) **Resulting uncertainty:** Propagate the uncertainties in the measured quantities X and input quantities $\mathbf{Z}_{0,1}$ and k through the function f to obtain the resulting uncertainty u_Y in the output measurand Y as

$$u_Y = \left(J^f U (J^f)^T \right)^{\frac{1}{2}}. \quad (\text{A.3})$$

The resulting matrix u_Y captures how uncertainties in the inputs X , $\mathbf{Z}_{0,1}$ and k propagate through the model function f to affect the uncertainty in Y . For more detailed insight, refer to the GUM [14].

Please note: Since k is determined beforehand by an observational quantity or by the CA model function h , it is treated as a given input quantity alongside its associated uncertainty u_k within the method.

Appendix B. Case study results

The case study evaluates three configurations—single elbow, double s-elbow and double elbow out-of-plane—at three different Reynolds numbers— 5×10^4 , 2.5×10^5 and 7×10^5 —representing practical operation points. Table B1 summarizes the results of the uncertainty evaluation methods, where Y_{cal} represents the calculated measurand Y , Y_{ref} the reference measurand value and the confidence intervals along with the uncertainty u_Y of the calculated measurand Y . These results demonstrate the performance of the methods across different flow conditions for specific application contexts.

Table B1. Case study results of flow meter benchmark application for single Elbow (SE), double S-Elbow (DSE) and double Elbow out-of-plane (DE).

Operation point Re = 5×10^4 (–)	Method LPU applied to DA				
	Y_{ref} (–)	Y_{cal} (–)	u_Y (–)	CI _{lower} (–)	CI _{upper} (–)
SE	50 078.806	50 078.806	251.168	49 586.515	50 571.096
DE	50 078.806	50 078.806	250.823	49 587.193	50 570.418
DSE	50 078.806	50 078.806	250.930	49 586.982	50 570.629

(Continued.)

Table B1. (Continued.)

Method LPU applied to VE-DA					
Operation point Re = 5×10^4 (-)	Y_{ref} (-)	Y_{cal} (-)	u_Y (-)	CI _{lower} (-)	CI _{upper} (-)
SE	50 078.806	50 078.806	255.669	49 577.694	50 579.918
DE	50 078.806	50 078.795	258.489	49 572.157	50 585.434
DSE	50 078.806	50 078.806	255.534	49 577.961	50 579.652
Method PoD applied to DA					
Operation point Re = 5×10^4 (-)	Y_{ref} (-)	Y_{cal} (-)	u_Y (-)	CI _{lower} (-)	CI _{upper} (-)
SE	50 078.806	50 078.894	251.093	49 586.751	50 571.037
DE	50 078.806	50 079.177	251.518	49 586.202	50 572.152
DSE	50 078.806	50 077.566	250.675	49 586.243	50 568.889
Method PoD applied to VE-DA					
Operation point Re = 5×10^4 (-)	Y_{ref} (-)	Y_{cal} (-)	u_Y (-)	CI _{lower} (-)	CI _{upper} (-)
SE	50 078.806	50 081.716	255.368	49 581.195	50 582.237
DE	50 078.806	50 079.062	258.072	49 573.240	50 584.884
DSE	50 078.806	50 081.940	255.131	49 581.884	50 581.995
Method LPU applied to DA					
Operation point Re = 2.5×10^5 (-)	Y_{ref} (-)	Y_{cal} (-)	u_Y (-)	CI _{lower} (-)	CI _{upper} (-)
SE	250 968.010	250 968.010	1271.866	248 475.153	253 460.867
DE	250 968.010	250 968.010	1260.735	248 496.970	253 439.050
DSE	250 968.010	250 968.010	1358.475	248 305.400	253 630.620
Method LPU applied to VE-DA					
Operation point Re = 2.5×10^5 (-)	Y_{ref} (-)	Y_{cal} (-)	u_Y (-)	CI _{lower} (-)	CI _{upper} (-)
SE	250 968.010	250 968.014	1289.495	248 440.605	253 495.424
DE	250 968.010	250 967.933	1294.435	248 430.839	253 505.026
DSE	250 968.010	250 968.015	1376.502	248 270.072	253 665.958
Method PoD applied to DA					
Operation point Re = 2.5×10^5 (-)	Y_{ref} (-)	Y_{cal} (-)	u_Y (-)	CI _{lower} (-)	CI _{upper} (-)
SE	250 968.010	250 964.824	1275.420	248 465.000	253 464.648
DE	250 968.010	250 971.038	1263.320	248 494.932	253 447.145
DSE	250 968.010	250 962.598	1363.182	248 290.761	253 634.434
Method PoD applied to VE-DA					
Operation point Re = 2.5×10^5 (-)	Y_{ref} (-)	Y_{cal} (-)	u_Y (-)	CI _{lower} (-)	CI _{upper} (-)
SE	250 968.010	250 983.413	1286.263	248 462.339	253 504.488
DE	250 968.010	250 977.126	1293.524	248 441.820	253 512.432
DSE	250 968.010	250 979.349	1378.413	248 277.659	253 681.039
Method LPU applied to DA					
Operation point Re = 7×10^5 (-)	Y_{ref} (-)	Y_{cal} (-)	u_Y (-)	CI _{lower} (-)	CI _{upper} (-)
SE	702 426.195	702 426.195	3528.007	695 511.302	709 341.088
DE	702 426.195	702 426.195	3567.354	695 434.181	709 418.208
DSE	702 426.195	702 426.195	3532.478	695 502.537	709 349.852

(Continued.)

Table B1. (Continued.)

Method LPU applied to VE-DA					
Operation point Re = 7×10^5 (-)	Y_{ref} (-)	Y_{cal} (-)	u_Y (-)	CI _{lower} (-)	CI _{upper} (-)
SE	702 426.195	702 426.203	3573.298	695 422.539	709 429.867
DE	702 426.195	702 426.039	3659.682	695 253.063	709 599.016
DSE	702 426.195	702 426.205	3579.238	695 410.897	709 441.512
Method PoD applied to DA					
Operation point Re = 7×10^5 (-)	Y_{ref} (-)	Y_{cal} (-)	u_Y (-)	CI _{lower} (-)	CI _{upper} (-)
SE	702 426.195	702 424.658	3528.312	695 509.166	709 340.149
DE	702 426.195	702 433.306	3558.888	695 457.886	709 408.726
DSE	702 426.195	702 426.049	3542.378	695 482.988	709 369.110
Method PoD applied to VE-DA					
Operation point Re = 7×10^5 (-)	Y_{ref} (-)	Y_{cal} (-)	u_Y (-)	CI _{lower} (-)	CI _{upper} (-)
SE	702 426.195	702 456.036	3575.765	695 447.536	709 464.536
DE	702 426.195	702 454.157	3625.226	695 348.714	709 559.601
DSE	702 426.195	702 496.849	3587.432	695 465.481	709 528.216

Appendix C. Factorial design space

For the selected baseline case, the results of a full $2^3 = 8$ factorial design study for the LPU applied to VE-DA are presented to demonstrate the influence of uncertainty in the input quantities Z_0 , Z_3 and Z_5 . Table C1 shows the results using the original uncertainties of the input quantities, while table C2 presents the results with a reduced uncertainty of $u_{Z_0} = 2 \times 10^{-5}$ of the dominant parameter Z_0 .

Table C1. Two-level full fractional design for LPU applied to VE-DA with original uncertainties.

Run	Z_0	Z_3	Z_5	u_Y
1	-1	-1	-1	14.810
2	-1	-1	+1	51.640
3	-1	+1	-1	19.091
4	-1	+1	+1	53.027
5	+1	-1	-1	253.711
6	+1	-1	+1	258.489
7	+1	+1	-1	253.711
8	+1	+1	+1	258.489

Table C2. Two-level full fractional design for LPU applied to VE-DA with reduced uncertainty of dominant quantity.

Run	Z_0	Z_3	Z_5	u_Y
1	-1	-1	-1	14.810
2	-1	-1	+1	51.640
3	-1	+1	-1	19.091
4	-1	+1	+1	53.027
5	+1	-1	-1	17.937
6	+1	-1	+1	52.622
7	+1	+1	-1	21.608
8	+1	+1	+1	53.984

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